

ACTION OF OXALYL CHLORIDE ON PHENOLIC ETHERS.

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Condensation of oxalyl chloride with phenolic ethers in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride gives rise to *o*-diketones in the cases of anisole and *o*-cresol-methyl ether, while with *m*-cresol- and *p*-cresol-methyl ethers, only the corresponding acids are obtained. With veratrole protocatechuic acid is obtained.

Liebermann and his coworkers have made extensive investigations on the action of oxalyl chloride on aromatic hydrocarbons (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 202, 852, 1453; 1912, **45**, 1186; 1913, **46**, 198) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and obtained in a majority of cases the corresponding mono-carboxylic acids. In a few cases, for instance with anthracene and *pp*-ditolyl, 1:2-diketones were obtained. We have investigated the action of oxalyl chloride on phenolic ethers, *e.g.*, anisole, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresol-methyl ethers and veratrole. With anisole, the diketone (anisil) is obtained in about 90% yield. This, by the way, seems to be the best method of preparing the substance. The diketone is identified by taking a mixed m. p. with a sample at hand and also by oxidising it with hydrogen peroxide to anisic acid (Hollemann, *Chem. Zentbl.*, 1904, **II**, 194).

With *o*-cresol methyl ether also a diketone is obtained along with a trace of an acid which could not be identified. The diketone gives on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide 4-methoxy-*m*-toluic acid, m. p. 192-93°. Its methyl ester melts at 67°.

m-Cresol methyl ether gives under exactly similar conditions 6-methylsalicylic acid, m. p. 167°. With *p*-cresol methyl ether also no diketone is obtained and 5-methylsalicylic acid, m. p. 149°, is the only product of the reaction. Veratrole gives protocatechuic acid, m. p. 189°, and no diketone is obtained.

Resorcinol dimethyl ether gives a tarry matter from which no product could be isolated. Hydroquinone dimethyl ether does not react at all, while with pyrogallol trimethyl ether, an acid mixture is obtained melting through a wide range of temperature, which could not be characterised.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Oxalyl Chloride with Anisole: Formation of Anisil.—In a three-necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser provided with a calcium chloride guard tube and a mechanical stirrer with mercury seal,

anisole (10 g.) was dissolved in carbon bisulphide (50 c. c.) and oxalyl chloride (6.3 g.) was added. The solution was cooled by means of a freezing mixture and freshly prepared and finely powdered aluminium chloride (20 g.) was added a little at a time, with vigorous stirring. Hydrochloric acid gas was evolved and after sometime a sticky solid separated at the bottom of the flask. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight, carbon bisulphide was removed by decantation and the reddish brown solid was treated with ice and hydrochloric acid and then heated on the water-bath. The solid was filtered, washed with water, digested with sodium carbonate solution and finally washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as greenish yellow needles, m. p. 132° (mixed m. p. with anisil), yield 90%. (Found: C, 71.06; H, 5.18. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$: C, 71.12; H, 5.17 per cent).

The sodium carbonate washings on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid and extraction with ether gave a small quantity of a solid, m. p. 153° (mixed m. p. with salicylic acid).

Oxidation of Anisil.—A solution of anisil (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid was treated with perhydrol (15 c. c.) and the whole heated at 70-80° for about 4 hours. The solution on cooling deposited white needles of anisic acid and a further quantity was obtained by diluting the filtrate. The combined solids were washed, dissolved in soda solution, reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid and the acid recrystallised from hot water (charcoal), m. p. 183°, yield about 2 g. (Found: C, 62.8; H, 5.37. Calc. for $C_8H_8O_3$: C, 63.17; H, 5.26 per cent).

Condensation of Oxalyl Chloride with o-Cresol methyl ether.—A mixture of *o*-cresol methyl ether (10 g.) in carbon bisulphide (50 c. c.) and oxalyl chloride (5 c. c.) was treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g.) and the product treated as in the previous case, m. p. 174°, yield of diketone about 5 g. (Found: C, 72.57; H, 5.33. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 72.48; H, 5.04 per cent).

Oxidation of the diketone (2 g.) with hydrogen peroxide gave 1.5 g. of 4-methoxy-*m* toluic acid. (Found: C, 65.43; H, 6.06. Calc. for $C_9H_{10}O_3$: C, 65.06; H, 6.02 per cent).

4:4'-Dimethoxy-3:3'-dimethylbenzilic Acid.—The above diketone (3 g.) was added to caustic soda (10 g.) and heated to about 180° in a nickel basin. It melted and the mixture solidified to a reddish substance. The cooled melt was dissolved in water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated acid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from hot water (charcoal), m. p. 145-47°. (Found: C, 68.52; H, 6.84. $C_{18}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 68.37; H, 6.33 per cent).

Condensation of Oxalyl Chloride with p-Cresol methyl ether.—The condensation was effected as in the previous cases but no diketone was obtained. With *p*-cresol methyl ether (10 g.), oxalyl chloride (10 c.c.) and aluminium chloride (15 g.) 5-methylsalicylic acid (1.6 g.), m.p. 149°, was the only product of the reaction. (Found: C, 64.52; H, 5.23. Calc. for $C_8H_8O_3$: C, 63.17; H, 5.26 per cent).

Condensation of Oxalyl Chloride with m-Cresol methyl ether.—A mixture of *m*-cresol methyl ether (10 c.c.), oxalyl chloride (10 c.c.) and carbon bisulphide (100 c.c.) was treated with aluminium chloride (20 g.) in the usual way. The only product was 3-methylsalicylic acid, m.p. 167-68°. (Found: C, 62.69; H, 5.44. Calc. for $C_8H_8O_3$: C, 63.17; H, 5.26 per cent).

Condensation of Oxalyl Chloride with Veratrole.—A mixture of veratrole (10 c.c.), oxalyl chloride (10 c.c.) and carbon bisulphide (75 c.c.) was treated with aluminium chloride (15 g.) in the usual way. The only product was protocatechuic acid, m.p. 189°, yield 2 g.